

BBMRI-LPC Large Prospective Cohorts

Grant Agreement no. 313010

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Deliverable No	D 9.5
Deliverable Title	Common Catalogue of Biobank Services (CCBS). Work shop and Report
Responsible Partner	NTNU

Final workshop “high quality biobanking”:

The 7th and final work shop was organized at HUNT Biobank, Levanger on Nov 28 and 29, 2016 with 43 participants from 19 different biobanks representing 5 LPC-partners.

The participants, discussions and reports were organized based on the four interest groups for high-quality biobanking already established, covering topics within most biobank processes, biobank services and quality studies.

We will continue to establish an overview of already published studies in the field of sample quality to agree on guidelines for pre-analytical handling in future studies and to recognize the areas where further testing/analysis needs to be done.

We will also follow-up ongoing work on selecting the most appropriate biomarkers for pre-analytic validation of biobank material from both

- a. population studies with known pre-analytical parameters
- b. clinical samples with known pre-analytical parameters and
- c. legacy collection with unknown pre-analytical parameters

Protocols for biobank based quality studies from all participating biobanks will continuously be uploaded to MolMeth for display and to form a basis for potentially larger, harmonized study protocols comprising multiple biobanks in order to increase the numbers and impact of such studies

All interest groups have expressed a clear motivation to continue their work beyond the project period of BBMRI-LPC, based on an existing transnational biobank network in close collaboration with the national biobank nodes as well as the Quality Manager at the BBMRI-ERIC HQ.

BRISQ has now been established as an interactive database (Ragic) and could be maintained by resources from BBMRI.no - CS-biobanking.

Common Catalogue of Biobank Services (CCBS):

An agreement was reached between the WP9-partners to publish the Common Catalogue of Biobank Services based on the data base solution similar to the one already in place for the **Biobank Analysis Resources Catalogue (BARC)**.

BARC is a freely available catalogue describing expertise and molecular analysis resources available at centers and companies for analysis of biobanked samples. It was initially designed for Centers and companies in Sweden, but was later expanded to also present similar resources in other European countries.

The catalogue is designed to inform researchers how to find suitable analysis techniques and their requirements. The resources are listed both by location at different centres and companies, technologies available and by contact personnel. BARC is developed and managed at the Department of Immunology, Genetics and Pathology, Uppsala University (UU), Sweden.

Negotiations are ongoing between UU, NTNU and BBMRI-ERIC to find a sustainable solution for a similar data base design for a Common Catalogue of Biobank Services beyond the BBMRI-LPC project period. BARC has presently only very limited funding and BBMRI.no/NTNU has been offered to take over the database and its source code/documentation, to be established as a Common Catalogue of Biobank Services elsewhere.

Both BARC and CCBS could be a great resource for the entire European biobank community and potentially maintained by BBMRI-ERIC and CS-IT. We have already discussed this with the Director General of BBMRI-ERIC, prof. Jan-Eric Litton and the plan is to present this challenge at the common AoM/MC-meeting in Lausanne in May. Following this discussion, the descriptions of the various biobank services throughout multiple European biobanks will be consecutively entered into the selected data base solution and eventually constitute the Common Catalogue of Biobank Service (CCBS). In this way we will both ensure sustainability and create a dynamic catalogue of significant value for all biobankers.